

On-line Optimal information-aware path planning with actuation noise and intermittent noisy measurements

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Abstract—In this work, we describe some recent research activities over the last years regarding an online optimal perception-aware strategy. The goal is to reduce at runtime the estimation uncertainty by maximizing the amount of information provided by the onboard sensors in spite of not negligible Gaussian or Brownian actuation/process noise and intermittent noisy measurements (e.g. in case of on-board limited field-of-view sensors).

Index Terms—Active sensing control, observability and reachability analysis, optimal control

I. INTRODUCTION

During the last 40 years, a great effort has been devoted by the robotic community in order to introduce some level of active sensing/perception control strategies in robotics tasks. Indeed, the several sources of variability and uncertainties that influence robotic systems may negatively affect the quality of the information coming from the on-board sensors and hence the possibility of correctly and precisely reconstruct the current state of the robot. However, most of literature [1], [2], [3] only considers the uncertainties provided by the noise affecting the sensor reading without explicitly taking into account the negative effects of the actuation/process noise, which are far from negligible in several robotic applications (e.g. in aerial vehicles or mobile ones moving on a rough terrain). Some exceptions can be found in [4], [5], [6]. In general, apart from very few works, the most of the above-cited approaches are more devoted to an offline implementation, while one of the objectives of this work is to provide an *online* strategy, as in [3], which is able to provide a new optimal trajectory as soon as an update of the current state estimation is provided by the employed observer, an Extended Kalman Filter (EKF) in our case. Also, those few jobs that deal with actuation/process noise, does not provide an explicit measure of the degrading effects of this source of noise in the estimation process.

Finally, in case of limited sensing range or Field-Of-View (FOV) it is the difficulty to guarantee the availability of a sufficient number of measurements able to ensure observability of the variables of interest for the robotic task. This problem of maintaining the maximum number of points of interest in view for the largest amount of time has been tackled in [2] and [7]. Also in [8], intermittent measurements availability has been cast

Fig. 1: Optimal active sensing control scheme. The control input \mathbf{u} maximizes the chosen information metric. The EKF receives the noisy sensor readings, the noisy input \mathbf{u} and the initial covariance matrix \mathbf{P}_0 and provides the current state estimation $\hat{\mathbf{q}}$ and the a posteriori covariance matrix \mathbf{P} that are then used to determine the next optimal information-aware control action \mathbf{u} .

in a minimum-time trajectory planning. However, in the latter case, the methodology is limited to Riccati observers.

In this work, as also described with more details in [9], we propose an online optimal perception-aware strategy meant to maximize the information collected along the planned trajectory using intermittently available measurements while minimizing the degrading effects of actuation/process noise. The main novelties of this work are: (i) the use of a norm of the Reachability Gramian (RG) for measuring the degrading effects of actuation/process noise and (ii) combine it with a norm of the Constructability Gramian (CG) (for measuring the information coming from sensors) in order to provide new effective combined information metrics.

II. CONTRIBUTIONS AND RESULTS

As introduced in the previous section, one of the main contributions of this paper is to propose an effective combination of the Reachability and Constructability Gramians capable of correctly handling intermittent measurements availability, e.g. limited sensing range or FOV, possibly resulting in intermittent full observability. A norm of the CG was already used to quantify the amount of collected information in [3] where, differently from this work, the actuation/process noise was considered negligible and measurements were always available during motion. The

information collected through sensors along the planned path increases the level of information by an amount quantifiable by some norm of CG, i.e. a function of its eigenvalues. The Reachability Gramian instead is usually adopted for quantifying and then optimize the effort required to drive a system towards a desired state [10] or to find the optimal actuator location [11]. However, it can be shown that the RG is related to the optimal estimation error covariance matrix P , solution of the Riccati equation when no measurements are available. Exploiting this relationship, in this work, a norm of the RG is used to quantify the degrading effects of the actuation/process noise along the planned path. Therefore, given a path, the actuation/process noise decreases the level of information by an amount quantifiable by some norm of RG, i.e. a function of its eigenvalues.

In practical applications, measurements and actuation noises act on the system simultaneously. For this reason, an effective combination of the above-mentioned Gramians should be directly used in order to improve state estimation for generic filters, such as Unscented Kalman Filters or Particle Filters. Based on the above discussion, we identified three information-aware cost functions as weighed sum of the smallest eigenvalues of the above-mentioned Gramians:

- 1) the first one, called J_0 , is the weighted sum of the smallest eigenvalues of the CG and the RG. By maximizing J_0 online, trajectories that simultaneously increase the sensor information and reduces the negative actuation effects along the highest uncertainty direction, depending on the number of available measurements and hence the degree of Constructability, are obtained.
- 2) J_1 considers the smallest eigenvalue of the sub-matrix of the RG projected along the null space of the CG. As a consequence, the negative effects of actuation/process noise of reducing the level of information are directed toward the direction with minimum uncertainty into the unobservable space, i.e. where, however, the sensor information can not be beneficial. The information content about the observable space can hence freely increase towards its maximum value.
- 3) J_2 considers the smallest eigenvalue of the sub-matrix of the RG projected along with the observable space of the CG. In this case, the negative effects of actuation/process noise are directed toward the direction with minimum uncertainty but still observable, i.e., where the sensor information can still be beneficial. As a consequence, the information content into the unobservable space remains as much as possible unchanged.

The three cost functions are optimized in the online optimal sensing control problem shown in fig. 1. CasADi tool [12] is used to solve it. Our methodology is applied to a unicycle vehicle equipped with a range sensor that provides intermittent measurements w.r.t. eight markers. Each measurement is available if the distance between the robot and the marker is less than 5 m. For modelling measurements noise, we will use the classical Gaussian hypothesis. The actuation noise also assumes a more degrading Brownian distribution.

To show the effectiveness of our proposed cost functions J_i , $i = 0, 1, 2$ w.r.t. the one proposed in [3], a statistical analysis was performed in case of Gaussian actuation/process noise. This test has shown that J_1 finds the more informative paths. In addition, we also consider a Brownian unicycle kinematic as described in [13]. The CG-based optimal path and J_1 -based one (the one that previously provided the best performance) are compared. In

(a) Real trajectories for J_1 and CG. (b) $\lambda_{\min}(P_f^{-1})$ is 2.1 for J_1 and 1.15 for CG.

Fig. 2: Comparison in terms of estimation performance for a Brownian unicycle dynamic.

this case, the J_1 -based optimal trajectory allows reaching the final configuration with the minimum estimation uncertainty (fig. 2).

III. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORKS

We have shown how our active sensing control methodology is able to simultaneously cope with the negative effects of actuation/process noise as well as with intermittent noisy measurements. Future works will be focused on finding a different and effective combination of the proposed cost indices and implementing it on more complex robotic systems (e.g. a quadrotor) in real-time. This technique constitutes a baseline for actively managing the risk of collision in an industrial environment shared with other robots and humans.

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